

Digital Banking In India: Benefits And Challenges

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Abstract

Digital banking is one of the most significant progress in Indian banking sector. Digital banking means making financial transactions by using technology and the internet. Digital banking helps the customer with quicker and simpler banking. Late in 1980, banks in India started adopting computer-based technology. Since the banking system adopted technology, the Indian economy has made considerable progress forward. Hence Understanding and assessing the current condition of digital banking is essential. This paper goal is to overview the various digital banking products and provide an outline of their benefits as well as their challenges.

Keywords: Digital Banking, Net Banking, Credit Card, Debit Card, NEFT, RTGS,

Introduction –

The banking sector is very important to the growth of the Indian economy. For the economy to develop, the banking system must be stable and strong. It facilitates the ability to establish and sustain a reliable payment system that satisfies the needs of enterprises, government and the general public. The Indian banking sector is now undergoing a revolution in digital technologies and moving fast towards digitization. In 1988, the RBI established a committee led by Dr. C. Rangrajan to study the need for digitalization in the banking sector in India in late 1980. Until 1990, banks were not actively involved in digital banking operations. In late 1990, ICICI bank was the first financial institution to offer these services to its Customer, permitting them to handle all banking activities from a location of their choosing. To provide financial services online, digital banking changed to online banking. It offers customers the fastest and most useful financial services.

As a result of the digital revolution, the banking sector is fast changing and increasing its financial transactions. Platforms like the Unified Payment Interface (UPI), Aadhar Pay, Debit Cards and Quick Payment Service are necessary for the digitalization of banking. The use of many current and developing technologies by banks may be seen as a component of digital banking. Bankers may use digital banking to meet their current as well as future technological and commercial needs.

Objectives -

1. To understand the concept of digital banking in India.
2. To know about the digital banking products of the Indian banking system.
3. To study the opportunity and challenges of digital banking.

Research Methodology –

For this article used only secondary sources, including reference books, Research Papers,

Websites, Journals and other research that have already been published elsewhere.

Digital Banking – Digital banking, generally referred to as e-banking, online banking or internet banking, is a system that makes it possible to conduct financial operations including payments, deposits, and cash withdrawals electronically over the internet rather than in person at bank branches. Digital banking services allow customers to complete financial activities according to their needs and preferences, such as balance inquiries, money transfers and bill payments by digital channels at the time and location of their choosing. The phrase "digital banking" describes financial transactions made via the use of technology and the internet. The majority of the bank's services are given to customers through its digital channels, which are quick and effective. With digital banking, customers can complete routine activities like bill payments, balance checks and statement downloads.

Digital Banking Products –

Digital banking products are described as follows.

ATM/Debit Card –

ATM are a popular resource for electronic payments. Customers of financial institutions can conduct their financial transactions by entering their authorized debit or credit cards into an Automated Teller Machine (ATM). The Customers will have access to banking services through the ATM, including cash withdrawals, deposits, bill payments, balance inquiries and card-to-card or card-to-account transfers, among other things. Also, it makes it easier for customers to swipe their cards at Point of Sale (POS) terminals at retail establishments to pay for products or services. The same card may also be used for online shopping and E-Commerce transactions.

Credit Card –

Customer can withdraw money from bank account using a credit card, without visiting the bank. Several debit card providers exist, including

Rupay, Visa and Mastercard. It makes it possible for Customers to make purchases without actually having cash on hand. The Customer can borrow money using a credit card within predetermined limits.

Mobile Banking-

Customers can conduct banking transactions and gather related information using a mobile phone or tablet anytime, anywhere 24/7 hours. This service is known as mobile banking. Clients can only access mobile banking when the bank offers the necessary applications or software. With its help, customers may manage insurance policies, monitor term deposits, view loan statements, download mini statements and get alerts on account activity.

NEFT-

The transaction may be made in 30 minutes using the National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT) system, which is a centralized cashless transaction. Banks transfer funds between one bank to another bank through the use of the NEFT mechanism. Bank branches must have NEFT activated to use this network. By using NEFT, a transaction must be made with the Indian Financial System Code (IFSC). The IFSC code is particular to every bank branch.

RTGS - Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS) is an ongoing procedure for settling funds on an individual order basis. Large-value transactions are the main purpose of the RTGS system. The Reserve Bank has discontinued the processing fees it assessed for RTGS transactions as of July 2019. Cheque must be used to complete this transaction.

IMPS –

The interbank electronic fund transfer service provided by IMPS is reliable and real-time and it is available instantly 24/7 hours. A strong service called IMPS makes it possible to send money rapidly between banks all throughout India. It is not only secure but also cost-effective.

Benefits of Digital Banking –

Digital banking has a lot of benefits. Customers that use digital banking are given several benefits by banks. Digital banking offers a variety of services, including ATM, mobile and online banking, debit and credit cards and more. Via this tool, customers may conveniently pay their invoices and other obligations. Digital banking makes it possible to carry out banking activities quickly. Time is saved by customers using digital banking. Banks are increasingly providing their customers the option of receiving their account statements online through digital banking. This reduces the operational expenses of banks and saves a significant quantity of paper and mail waste. Due to this, banks are now able to provide services at cheaper costs and with better interest rates on

deposits. Bank earnings have increased due to lower operational costs. This indicates that some of the savings can be distributed to the clientele in the form of greater rates on deposits and reduced rates on loans. Customers may access their bank accounts 24/7 without going to a branch. The transactions carried out using mobile banking applications are rapid, simple, and secure. With the advent of digital banking, the majority of the rural population has engaged in banking activities. People can also do their business online. The number of Customers for banks has grown due to the increasing convenience of anytime, anywhere banking. It is feasible to produce reports because electronic records of every transaction are kept.

Challenges of Digital Banking –

Digital banking offers many advantages, but it also has certain drawbacks. For banks, the security issue has grown to be one of their top priorities. Due to worries about security, a sizable portion of clients reject digital banking options. Cybercrime danger has escalated as a result of digital banking. Cyber assaults can affect the majority of banking and financial applications. Some hackers use cutting-edge methods to steal money, often in big sums all at once. There is also always a risk that priceless personal data will be stolen. Since the introduction of digital banking, online hackers have increased their activity. These individuals commit fraud by building a bogus bank website. To protect themselves from dangers from cybercrime, banks must make sure that their system is updated and well-maintained. It's a major problem for the banking sector. Customers' security worries will be allayed if this, which might lead to an increase in the usage of digital banking. For most clients, trust is the main barrier to digital banking. The majority of clients prefer the individualized attention and services provided by bank branch employees. Due to a lack of confidence in internet security, clients choose traditional banking. Because they believe that transactions made online are dangerous. A person who understands finances is more inclined to use digital banking services and channels. India still has extremely low levels of digital literacy. More than 90% of Indians, according to the Internet and Mobile Association of India Report (IAMAI), are virtually completely digitally illiterate. 76 percent of Indian people, or seven percentile points less than the global index, are unable to comprehend basic financial concepts, according to a Standard & Poor's Financial Services LLC poll. Complete digital banking is now restricted by a lack of online accessibility, a slow internet connection. People are not interested in digital activities in rural locations because of poor internet access and even misdirected telecom signals. Thus, the network system should be corrected by the

government and lower internet prices to provide universal access for digital banking.

Conclusion –

The change from cash and paper-based banking to cashless and paperless banking has begun as a result of banking's digitalization. Indian banks are dealing with possibilities and problems in the current financial environment related to digital banking. By applying digitization in the banking sector, clients may now access the bank's goods and services whenever and wherever it's convenient for them. Internet banking, mobile banking, UPI payments, QR codes, mobile wallets and other financial technologies were made available to its customers. For counterweight and security measures, banks can also embrace more cutting-edge techniques and technology. Now, transactions can be made every day of the year. With the digital banking platform, certain transactions, like paying bills or regular payments can be automated. Without a question, the introduction of digitalization has increased competition in the Indian banking sector. To make digital banking widespread, the Indian banking sector will need to overcome some obstacles. To make the digital dream a reality, internet access and related digital infrastructure must be guaranteed. The possibility of cyber attacks is another factor. It will be fascinating to observe how the banking sector handles these difficulties. Here, the government as well as other relevant parties must play a significant role.

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